

REFORMS IN THE MANAGEMENT OF PUBLIC SCHOOLS IN UZBEKISTAN AND THEIR RESULTS

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Abstract. *This article provides a scientific-analytical overview of the reforms in the management of general education schools in Uzbekistan, including their content, implementation mechanisms, and practical outcomes. In the research process, normative legal documents, statistical data, international experience, and existing scientific sources were used as a basis.*

Keywords: *school management, reform, sector, education system, world education systems, cooperation with parents and the public, competencies, modern school.*

INTRODUCTION

The large-scale reforms implemented in the Uzbek education system in recent years are aimed at modernizing the management of general education schools, increasing the efficiency of the teaching process, the development of students' competencies and the creation of an educational environment that meets international standards. School governance is a crucial link that ensures the quality of education, the alignment of the learning process, the competence of teaching staff, student achievement, and collaboration with parents and the community. Therefore, reforms in this area are considered one of the key priority directions for the country's development.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODOLOGY

The necessity of management reforms in Uzbekistan's education system stems from the fact that, since the early years of independence, a number of systemic problems have accumulated in general education schools. In particular:

- highly centralized management;
- the insufficient management capacity of school principals,
- a weak incentive system for teachers,
- outdated material and technical base,
- sharp regional disparities in the quality of education;
- weak development of public-private partnerships.

These problems laid the groundwork for the launch of a new phase of reforms beginning in 2017. The competition in global education systems, the rapid development of digital technologies, and the growing demand for competency-based education also required the modernization of Uzbekistan's schools. Therefore, the reforms were aligned with the following key global requirements: preparing for international assessment programs (PISA, TIMSS), introducing STEM and digital education elements, conducting school governance with public participation, and others.

In Uzbekistan, the management of general education schools—covering its content, directions, and reforms—is the activity of effectively organizing and monitoring the teaching process, educational work, and financial and organizational processes. The purpose of this management is to ensure the quality of education, student achievement, and the school's competitiveness.

RESULTS

Management covers the following key areas:

Managing pedagogical processes (curriculum, lesson plans, assessment)

Managing staff (teacher selection, skill development, motivation)

Organizational management (document management, planning, internal regulations)

Financial management (budget, income, expenses)

Collaboration with parents (social partnership)

The school's relationship with external institutions (municipality, kindergartens, colleges, ministries)

Regarding the reforms in school management in Uzbekistan, it should be noted that in recent years the education system has been fundamentally reformed, and many innovations aimed at making school management effective have been introduced. In digital educational management, this includes electronic diaries and journals, electronic staff registration, and online monitoring of the educational process, strengthening the principal's institution, an attestation and selection system for principals, expanding the authority of deputy principals, an increased focus on management competencies, the gradual transition of schools toward financial independence, the establishment of "Management Boards" the introduction of public-private partnership principles, and the effective use of sponsorship funds. A new model for monitoring the quality of education: the activities of the National Assessment Center, preparation for the PIRLS, TIMSS, and PISA international assessments, and the introduction of diagnostic tests. In the system for encouraging teachers' activities, annual attestation and the mentor-mentee system, as well as the "Best Teacher" and "Most Exemplary School" competitions, are recommended. In Uzbekistan, modern school management is based on the following principles:

- openness and transparency
- results-orientedness
- innovative approach
- collective management
- Partnership with stakeholders
- Student-centered education.

When referring to a modern model of school governance, today's schools are transitioning to the following integrated management model:

1. In strategic management, this refers to the school's 3–5 year development strategy and targeted programs (STEAM, digital education, inclusive education).

2. In operational management, we understand the lesson schedule, distribution of subject teachers, and teaching and educational plans.

3. In innovative management, it involves establishing STEAM laboratories, robotics, media education, and introducing advanced pedagogical technologies into the teaching process.

The problems encountered in the management of general education schools today

- insufficient qualifications of personnel;
- unequal material and technical resources in schools;
- disparities in educational quality between regions;
- low parental involvement;
- weak external monitoring.

Regular training for school principals in management psychology and management, Creation of a "School Digital Dashboard," strengthening a tripartite accountability system among the principal, teachers, and parents, creation of a program to equalize educational quality across regions, and strengthening cooperation with the private sector. In recent years, the development of the education system, particularly public schools, has remained one of the top priorities of state policy in our country. At a time when Uzbekistan is striving for an innovative economy, the role of schools in ensuring quality education, preparing competitive personnel, and developing the creativity and scientific potential of young people is invaluable. This, in turn, requires modern, transparent, and performance-based approaches to school management. To this end, a number of state programs, resolutions, and decrees have been adopted regarding the management of public schools. They place special emphasis on issues such as modernizing schools, improving management, enhancing the qualifications of principals, creating a new system for assessing the quality of education, digitization, and raising the prestige of educators.

The analysis involves examining the content of the reforms being implemented in the management of general education schools in Uzbekistan, evaluating their effectiveness, and providing scientifically based proposals for existing problems. Temurid Mirzo Ulugh Beg built an observatory in Samarkand in the 15th century and drew up a star chart. He calculated the positions of the stars so accurately that modern science and technology have determined these data differ from today's calculations by only one or two minutes. From this, it is clear that our forefathers were individuals who made a worthy contribution to world civilization. Essentially, the education system was subordinated to the interests of the former center's ruling ideology. Let's say that most subjects were not included in the curriculum. Take Uzbek history as an example: it was not taught impartially, and the majority of the hours allocated to it in the curriculum were devoted to studying the history of the former Soviet Union. Students' minds were filled with misinterpreted events from our country's history. National values and spirituality were trampled, and the lives and creative paths of genuine Uzbek scholars and great statesmen and commanders were denigrated.

After our country gained independence, fundamental changes began to be implemented in all sectors. Particular attention was paid to the education sector. As the education and upbringing system improved, people's spirituality, consciousness, and scope of thought were shaped and elevated." It was necessary to comprehensively reform and renew the education system in both form and content. After all, at a time when society demands the upbringing of a new individual, it is impossible to build a new society without changing and modernizing people's consciousness, worldview, and level of knowledge. Our first President, Islam Karimov, during the years of independence, taking these aspects into account, paid great attention to education and upbringing in order to form a new worldview in people based on our national values and traditions. Education

infuses the spirituality of the Uzbek people with creative activity, All the best potential of the rising generation will be revealed, their professions and skills will continuously improve, and the wise experience of older generations will be understood and passed on to the younger generation.

DISCUSSION

According to the latest information on education, President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev on September 23, 2020 The Ministry of Justice press service reported that President Shavkat Mirziyoyev signed the new edition of the Law "On Education" on May 19. The document was adopted by deputies of the Legislative Chamber of the Oliy Majlis in a second reading on by the Senate on August 7. The document was adopted by deputies of the Legislative Chamber of the Oliy Majlis on May 19 in its second reading and approved by the Senate on August

7. According to the law, the types of education are as follows.

- Preschool education and upbringing;
- General secondary and secondary vocational education:
- Vocational education:
- Higher education:
- Postgraduate education:
- Professional development and retraining of personnel:
- Non-formal education:

General secondary education includes grades 1–11. Secondary vocational education is carried out in academic lyceums over two years based on a nine-year basic secondary education. Vocational education is divided into initial, secondary, and higher secondary vocational education levels. Initial vocational education is provided free of charge in vocational schools for 9th-grade graduates in a two-year integrated day program. Secondary professional education is carried out in colleges on a state-funded or fee-contract basis in full-time, evening, and correspondence modes, with a duration of up to two years. Secondary professional education is carried out in technical schools on a state commission or contract basis in full-time, evening, and correspondence forms with a duration of at least two years. According to the law, state higher education institutions, institutions of secondary specialized professional education, and their branches are established by decrees of the President or the government.

Licenses for non-state educational organizations are issued by the State Inspectorate for Quality Control in Education. The establishment of non-state educational institutions is carried out by their founders. This law enters into force on the day of its official publication. The most effective investment is one made in education. It is about improving the education system, enhancing students' knowledge, and raising its quality standards. Therefore, the President stated, "The teaching profession must be the most prestigious and respected profession in society," and emphasized that a system for paying bonuses to teachers and educators would be introduced in our country in 2021. It is fitting to say that this initiative is a consistent continuation of the practical activities and measures to raise the social prestige and status of teachers and mentors over the past four years. In response to these initiatives put forward by our President, we must study and learn more than ever and work even harder on ourselves, The imperative of our time is that we become children, personnel, and specialists who will be not only a pillar for our people and our homeland, but also a source of confidence in tomorrow and those who will shape its future.

I would also like to add that in the years following our country's independence, the reforms taking place in the higher education system—specifically the opportunities for applicants to enter higher education institutions—have grown from the single-university option of previous years to

three universities in 2019 and five in 2020, which is great news for applicants. Of course, these measures have been a great impetus for prospective students, increasing their opportunities and accelerating their interest in studying. Another change outlined in the new education law is that the school entry age for children is now strictly set at 7 years, instead of the previous 6–7 years. I would like to quote an important point our President made in his address to the people. The address reads, in part, as follows. To raise the prestige of the title "teacher" in the school system, it is necessary to increase their moral and material support, and for this, to raise their monthly salaries, in particular, the appeal emphasizes that our President has stressed the need to increase the monthly salaries of teachers to raise the prestige of the profession. Specifically, a 50% salary supplement should be established for teachers who work in a different district, and a 100% supplement for those who work in another region.

CONCLUSION

In general education schools, management is a comprehensive system that includes organizing, evaluating, and monitoring the teaching and learning process, coordinating the activities of educators, and managing the school's material, financial, and organizational processes. The management process is carried out through the following main components:

Strategic management optimizes processes focused on educational quality by developing the school's development strategy and setting long-term goals.

Operational management - curriculum and subject distribution, class schedule, plan for extracurricular activities, coordination of teachers' activities

Innovative management - implementation of STEAM technologies, robotics and media education, use of digital educational resources, enhancing teachers' digital competence.

Monitoring and evaluation - quality of education indicators, diagnostic tests, student achievement results, monitoring of pedagogical activities.

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